

Guide to uploading data on Zenodo

1. Sign up for an account at zenodo.org/signup/.

The image shows the Zenodo sign-up page. At the top, the Zenodo logo is displayed in white on a blue background. Below the logo, the text "Research. Shared! Sign up today." is centered. The page is divided into two main sections: text on the left and a sign-up form on the right.

Citeable. Discoverable.
Uploads get a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to make them easily and uniquely citeable.

Communities
Accept or reject uploads to your own community (e.g workshops, EU projects, institutions or entire disciplines).

Trusted Research Data Management
Built on top of CERN's expertise in managing 100s of petabytes of research data from the Large Hadron Collider.

The sign-up form on the right includes the following elements:

- Two buttons for social login: "Sign up with GitHub" and "Sign up with ORCID".
- A separator: "— OR —".
- Three input fields: "Email Address", "Username", and "Password".
- A checkbox labeled "I'm not a robot" next to a reCAPTCHA logo and the text "reCAPTCHA Privacy - Terms".
- A large orange "Sign Up" button at the bottom.

Guide to uploading data on Zenodo

2. Login and then go to upload the top of the window.

Click here

zenodo

Search

Upload Communities

ekaroune@googlemail.com

Featured communities

Need help uploading? [Contact us](#)

National COVID Cohort Collaborative

National COVID Cohort Collaborative (N3C)

The National COVID Cohort Collaborative (N3C) is a complementary and synergistic partnership among the Clinical and Translational Science Awards (CTSA) Program hubs, the National Center for Data to Health (CD2H), distributed clinical data networks (PCORnet, OHDSI, ACT/i2b2, TriNetX), and other...

Curated by: CD2H

Guide to uploading data on Zenodo

3. Click green New Upload button.

Click here

The screenshot shows the Zenodo website interface. At the top, there is a blue navigation bar with the Zenodo logo on the left, a search bar, and links for 'Upload' and 'Communities'. On the right side of the navigation bar, there is a user profile dropdown menu showing 'ekaroune@googlemail.com'. Below the navigation bar, there is a search bar for uploads. To the right of the search bar, there is a green button labeled 'New Upload' with a circular arrow icon. An orange arrow points from the text 'Click here' to this button. Below the search bar, there is a list of uploads. The first upload is titled 'Open Science Skills Workshop for the Association for Environmental Archaeology' and is dated 'November 21, 2021 (v1)'. It is labeled as a 'Presentation' and 'Open Access'. The second upload is titled 'Reproducible Research in Archaeology' and is dated 'October 15, 2021 (2.0)'. It is also labeled as a 'Presentation' and 'Open Access'. Below the second upload, there is a note: '1 more version(s) exist for this record'. At the top right of the list, there are sorting options: 'Sort Most recent' and 'asc.'.

4. Fill in the form about your data.

Tips:

- You don't have to fill it all in at once.
- Click Save button to save your progress when filling it in.
- Only when you click the Publish button will it be seen by others on the repository.
- You can reserve a DOI (to put on your publication) and publish at a future date (when submitted to the journal).

The screenshot shows the Zenodo 'New upload' form. At the top right, there are buttons for 'Delete', 'Save', and 'Publish'. The main area is titled 'New upload' and contains instructions, a 'Files' section with 'Choose files' and 'Start upload' buttons, a 'Communities' section with a search box, an 'Upload type' section with various icons (Publication, Poster, Presentation, Dataset, Image, Video/Audio, Software, Lesson, Physical object, Other), a 'Publication type' dropdown menu, and a 'Basic information' section. The 'Basic information' section includes a 'Digital Object Identifier' field with the value 'e.g. 10.1234/foo.bar', a 'Reserve DOI' button, and a 'Publication date' field with the value '2021-12-27'. Orange arrows from the tips point to the 'Save' button, the 'Publish' button, and the 'Reserve DOI' button.

Delete Save Publish

New upload

Instructions: (i) Upload minimum one file or fill-in required fields (marked with a red star). (ii) Press "Save" to save your progress for editing later. (iii) When ready, press "Publish" to finalize and make your upload public.

Files Choose files Start upload

Drag and drop files here
– or –
Choose files

(minimum 1 file required, max 50 GB per dataset - contact us for larger datasets)
If you're experiencing issues with uploading larger files, read our FAQ section on file upload issues.

Communities recommended

Specify communities which you wish your upload to appear in. The owner of the community will be notified, and can either accept or reject your request. Please make sure your record complies with the content policy of the communities you add; reported abuse will be followed by account inactivation.

Start typing a community name...

Upload type required

Publication Poster Presentation Dataset Image Video/Audio Software Lesson Physical object Other

Publication type Journal article
Publication type

Basic information required

Digital Object Identifier e.g. 10.1234/foo.bar
Optional. Did your publisher already assign a DOI to your upload? If not, leave the field empty and we will register a new DOI for you. A DOI allows others to easily and unambiguously cite your upload. Please note that it is NOT possible to edit a Zenodo DOI once it has been registered by us, while it is always possible to edit a custom DOI.

Reserve DOI

Publication date * 2021-12-27
Required. Format: YYYY-MM-DD. In case your upload was already published elsewhere, please use the date of first publication.

Guide to uploading data on Zenodo

4. Fill in the form about your data

Drag and drop your data file here or choose file to upload

The screenshot shows the 'New upload' form on Zenodo. At the top, there are 'Delete', 'Save', and 'Publish' buttons. Below is the 'Files' section with a 'Choose files' button and a 'Start upload' button. The main area contains a 'Drag and drop files here' instruction and a 'Choose files' button. Below this is a 'Communities' section with a search box. The 'Upload type' section has icons for Publication, Poster, Presentation, Dataset, Image, Video/Audio, Software, Lesson, Physical object, and Other. The 'Publication type' dropdown is set to 'Journal article'. The 'Basic information' section includes a 'Digital Object Identifier' field with the value 'e.g. 10.1234/foo bar', a 'Reserve DOI' button, and a 'Publication date' field with the value '2021-12-27'.

You then **start upload** of the file. Note: this does not upload it in the repository, just on this upload form

If you want to link your data to a particular community, you can add that here by typing the name

Select dataset here

Press Reserve DOI here and the DOI will pop up in the box above

You can change the publication date here

Guide to uploading data on Zenodo

4. Fill in the form about your data.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo upload form with the following fields and annotations:

- Title ***: A text input field with an orange arrow pointing to it from the instruction "Fill in the title of your dataset here".
- Authors ***: Three input fields for "Family name, given names", "Affiliation", and "ORCID (e.g.: 0000-0002-1825-0097)". An orange arrow points to the ORCID field from the instruction "Add the Authors names and their ORCID numbers here".
- Description ***: A rich text editor with a toolbar. An orange arrow points to the text area from the instruction "Write a short description of the dataset here (this can be edited even after publication on Zenodo):".
- Version**: A text input field with an orange arrow pointing to it from the instruction "Usually this will be done for you as version 1.0 but if you want to give a different number add it here".
- Language**: A text input field with an orange arrow pointing to it from the instruction "Add in what language is used in the dataset".
- Keywords**: A text input field with an orange arrow pointing to it from the instruction "Add keywords such as: Phytoliths, Archaeology, Palaeoecology, country names".
- Additional notes**: A text input field at the bottom.

Fill in the title of your dataset here

Add the Authors names and their ORCID numbers here

Write a short description of the dataset here (this can be edited even after publication on Zenodo):

- Link to the article publication
- Link to other documentation about the dataset
- Link to a data paper

Usually this will be done for you as version 1.0 but if you want to give a different number add it here

Add in what language is used in the dataset

Add keywords such as: Phytoliths, Archaeology, Palaeoecology, country names

Guide to uploading data on Zenodo

4. Fill in the form about your data.

License required

Access right *

- Open Access
- Embargoed Access
- Restricted Access
- Closed Access

Required. Open access uploads have considerably higher visibility on Zenodo.

License *

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

Required. Selected license applies to all of your files displayed on the top of the form. If you want to upload some of your files under different licenses, please do so in separate uploads. If you cannot find the license you're looking for, include a relevant LICENSE file in your record and choose one of the *Other* licenses available (*Other (Open)*, *Other (Attribution)*, etc.). The supported licenses in the list are harvested from opendefinition.org and spdx.org. If you think that a license is missing from the list, please contact us.

Funding recommended

Zenodo is integrated into reporting lines for research funded by the European Commission via [OpenAIRE](https://openaire.eu). Specify grants which have funded your research, and we will let your funding agency know!

Grants

European Commission (EU)

Optional. OpenAIRE-supported projects only. For other funding acknowledgements, please use the *Additional Notes* field.
Note: a human Zenodo curator will need to validate your upload - you may experience a delay before it is available in OpenAIRE.

[+](#) Add another grant

Related/alternate identifiers recommended

Contributors optional

References optional

Journal optional

Journal title

Optional.

Choose the access you want - we suggest open but there are other options

Add a license - CC0 or CC-BY 4.0 are best for data

Add any funding information for the creation of the dataset

Add information about the publication it is link to here

Guide to uploading data on Zenodo

4. Fill in the form about your data.

Conference optional >

Book/Report/Chapter optional >

Thesis optional >

Subjects optional >

Delete Save Publish

You can link to other publications that use this dataset or conference paper if you wish

5. Save and then publish!

- Keep clicking the Save button as you add information about your dataset.
- You can go off the page and come back to it.
- Once you are happy with all of the information, press Save and then Publish.

NOTE

- If you do decide that you need to edit the information - this can be done and it will keep the same DOI.
- If you want to change the dataset - you can press Edit, upload another file and then Publish.
- This will be published as a different version of the dataset so will have a different DOI.